

CRAFTER 2.0: Perangkat lunak berbasis LLM untuk pembuatan persona

Goal: Controlled experiment to evaluate CRAFTER's usability using SUS and TAM

Activity	Methods/Details	Duration	Notes (Prompts and Resources)
Introduction	Facilitators introduce themselves as well as present the aim and goal of the experiment.	5 minutes	On-boarding participants on the experiment: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Research objective ● Activities: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Task ○ Survey ○ Interview
Controlled experiment	Participants read brief summary of how mHealth app users generally are	10 minutes	Facilitators provides brief summary of mHealth apps users' characteristics
	Facilitators provide the participants with GDrive link containing supplementary files	5 minutes	Supplementary files: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Task ● Files for RAG/knowledge base
	Participants perform the experiment: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Ask participants to create an account on the app ● Participants use CRAFTER to create persona as per instruction 	30 minutes	Link for GDrive to store participants' resulted personas
Survey	Participants fill in the questionnaire	20 minutes	Link Google Form
Interview	Facilitators ask several open-ended questions as follow-up	15 minutes	Interview script
Closing	Facilitators thank the participants for their participation	5 mins	